

doi:10.5281/zenodo.15160521

Influence of Educational Resource Management on Students Academic Performance in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis

Dr. Ngozi Stella OMODU

**Department of Educational Management,
Faculty of Education,
Rivers State University, Port Harcourt, Nigeria
omodu.morgan@ust.edu.ng/08133674661**

ABSTRACT

The study examined Influence of Educational Resource Management on Students Academic Performance in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis. The study was guided by three objectives from which three research questions and three hypotheses were derived. The study adopted a descriptive survey design with a population of 27,082 teachers and students comprising 25,077 students and 2,005 teachers in the 37 public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt and Obio/Akpor Local Government Areas of Rivers State. The sample size of the study was 728 respondents comprising 394 students and 334 teachers. The sample size was determined using Taro Yamene's formula. The multi-stage sampling technique was adopted in selecting the sample of the study. The instrument for data collection was a questionnaire titled "Influence of Educational Resource Management on Students Academic Performance in Public Senior Secondary Schools Questionnaire". The questionnaire was validated by experts in Rivers State University. Cronbach Alpha method was used to determine the reliability of the instrument. Reliability coefficients of 0.79, 0.81 and 0.83 were obtained for the various clusters of the instrument. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation statistics while the hypotheses were tested using z-test statistics at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that physical resource, human resource and financial resource management influence students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis to a high extent. The study recommends among others that, Government should make sure that the resources allocated to the education sectors are properly and judiciously utilized so as to bring about good result.

Keywords: Influence, Educational Resource, Management, Students, Academic Performance, Public, Senior Secondary Schools, Port Harcourt Metropolis.

INTRODUCTION

Resources play a critical role in the advancement of high-quality education. An educational system's ability to succeed or fail is determined by the calibre and quantity of resources provided to it. In any case, resources refer to the funds, people, and materials available to achieve organizational objectives. The level of availability and use may have a significant impact on how well an organization performs. Adeogun (2018) states that the term "educational resource" refers to the entirety of the input used in the educational system. Everything that is utilized, both directly and indirectly, to assist, facilitate, influence, or encourage the transmission or acquisition of competence, skills, and know-how is referred to as a resource. According to Ekundayo (2010), resources in education are all the things required for the education system to function properly. These consist of financial, material, physical, and human resources.

Human resources in education are the students, teaching staff, non-teaching staff, bursar, librarian, laboratory attendants, clerks, messengers, mail runners, gatekeepers, gardeners, and cooks as well as educational planners and administrators.

Material resources include textbooks, charts, maps, audio-visual and electronic instructional materials such as radio, tape recorder, television and video tape recorder. Other category of material resources consists of paper supplies and writing materials such as biro, eraser, exercise books, crayon, chalk, drawing books, notebooks, pencil, ruler, slate, workbook, etc.

Physical resources include classrooms, lecture theatres, auditoriums, typing pools, administrative block, libraries, laboratories, workshops, gymnasias, and assembly halls, special rooms like sickbay, staff quarters, students' hostels, kitchen, cafeteria, lavatory and toilet.

Financial resources are the monetary inputs available for and expended on the education system. These include money allocated to education by the government grants, PTA levy, and donations from philanthropists and internally generated funds.

Resource management implies the coordination of the resources (men, materials and money) in an organization in the right direction for the attainment of organizational goals. Since education is an organization where men, material, and money are needed for the production of output (graduates). Therefore, resources management in education is the proper coordination of the resources made available to the education sector for the purpose of producing quality graduates in the system. According to Babalola (2016), a competent educational manager must handle the funds, supplies, and equipment entrusted to them—including computers, teaching technologies, and internet access—with caution and effectiveness. Resource management, according to Banjoko (2020), is the efficient procurement, use, and upkeep of the materials required by the educational system. Babalola (2016) notes that while resource management is emphasized as the magic bullet for achieving high-quality output in the educational system, competent educational managers must handle the resources entrusted to them with care and efficiency, especially the funds, materials, and equipment such as computers, teaching technology, and internet access.

Students' performance in school depends to a great extent on the management of schools' available resources in terms of physical, human, material and financial resources towards the achievement of educational goals. The school is a complex social institution. It is an organization that deals with management of the available human, material, physical and financial resources for effective teaching and improvement of students' academic performance. Students' academic performance can be measured in many ways but the commonly used method is the result of students in public examinations, which is used to pass judgments on the schools and teachers. Ayo (2020) defines students' academic performance as outcome of students' assessments through comprehensive, systematic, cumulative, diagnostic, formative and summative evaluation of what they have gone through in a school setting. According to Ogunsaju (2018), academic performance of students is defined as desired changes or outcomes in their performance following a period of instruction and learning activities related to educational objectives that inform parents, teachers, administrators, and students about the extent to which educational objectives have been met. Academic performance is defined by Umoh (2017) as the final grade that a student receives following a thorough and methodical assessment of each individual student in a classroom setting with the aim of making decisions or rendering judgements regarding the cognitive, affective, and psychomotor domains of the student. The researcher considered students' academic performance to be their educational results as determined by the Senior Secondary School Certificate Examinations for the purposes of this study. Students' academic achievement is therefore influenced by the efficient use of both human and material resources in schools.

An educational system's potential to succeed or fail is dependent on both the availability of resources and their sensible and cautious management. The following justification for resource management in education was provided by Ekundayo (2020).

- i. To ensure that resources (materials and machines) are properly maintained so as to increase their life spans, hence reducing the cost of replacing them.

- ii. To ensure that the little resources (money) made available to the education sector are judiciously utilized. The provision of adequate resources and their efficient utilization are factors that determine the quality of education in any country.
- iii. To ensure quality control. Resources, if well managed, would ensure quality control. The quality of input in an educational system determines, to a very reasonable extent, the quality of output.
- iv. It helps to ensure better academic performance. The quality of school management of human and material resources has a very strong relationship to the students' academic performance.
- v. To ensure a very healthy education environment. Human resources represent the most valuable asset in an educational institution. Hence, human resource management can help fulfill the potential and increase the loyalty of the workforce while minimizing the cost and complexity of the administrative environment.

Technical and human skills are required for resource management in education, according to Olagboye (2018). The ability to use the instruments, procedures, processes, methods, and techniques of a specialized field with proficiency is referred to as technical skill. In this instance, education serves a specific purpose. Technical abilities are necessary for teachers and school administrators to make the most use of the resources that are available, including teachers, facilities, and equipment.

Conversely, interpersonal skills are essential for all administrative levels and are known as human skills. A formal and social organization like the educational system and organization cannot succeed in its goals and objectives without an awareness of itself and the members of the group. In order to accomplish the curriculum goals and educational goals through the accomplishment of instructional objectives, the school administrator, or principle, should cultivate a positive working relationship with the members of their staff.

Statement of the Problem

The purpose of secondary schools in Nigeria is to prepare students for postsecondary education and alternative professional paths. This makes the educational attainment level crucial since it dictates the calibre of labour force that will be employed in different economic sectors. Regretfully, it has been noted that student's interest in attending school is declining. Even worse, most students have a terrible attitude towards studying, which has negatively impacted their academic performance in the public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis. The poor utilization of educational resources in managing public schools has led to increasing cases of cultism and other juvenile delinquencies among students because they no longer see the school as a place of learning and it has affected students' academic performance. The reported poor performance of students in the West African Senior Secondary Examination is a testament of this fact (Adeyemi, 2021).

This poor students' academic performance has been attributed to a number of factors as seen in several studies carried out by other researchers. Some have attributed it to poor human, physical, material and financial resources, which also points at poor funding of public schools, shortage of teachers and so on. Not much has been done in ascertaining how educational resource management affects students' academic performance. Consequently, there is a dearth of literature in this area. The question then is could the educational resource management influence students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis? Providing answers to this question is the problem of this study.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to examine the influence of educational resource management on students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis. Specifically, the study sought to achieve the following objectives:

1. Determine the extent to which physical resource management influence students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis.
2. Find out the extent to which human resource management influence students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis.
3. Ascertain the extent to which financial resource management influence students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

1. To what extent does which physical resource management influence students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis?
2. To what extent does human resource management influence students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis?
3. To what extent does financial resource management influence students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of teachers and students on the extent to which physical resource management influence students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of teachers and students on the extent to which human resource management influence students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis.
3. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of teachers and students' teachers on the extent to which financial resource management influence students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a descriptive survey design with a population of 27,082 teachers and students comprising 25,077 students and 2,005 teachers in the 37 public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt and Obio/Akpor Local Government Areas of Rivers State. The sample size of the study was 728 respondents comprising 394 students and 334 teachers. The sample size was determined using Taro Yamene's formula. The multi-stage sampling technique was adopted in selecting the sample of the study. The instrument for data collection was a questionnaire titled "Influence of Educational Resource Management on Students Academic Performance in Public Senior Secondary Schools Questionnaire". Responses to the questionnaire items were structured on a four- point summated rating scale of: Very High Extent (VHE) – 4points, High Extent (HE) – 3points, Low Extent (LE) – 2points and Very Low Extent (VLE). The questionnaire was validated by experts in Rivers State University. Cronbach Alpha method was used to determine the reliability of the instrument. Reliability coefficients of 0.79, 0.81 and 0.83 were obtained for the various clusters of the instrument. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation statistics while the hypotheses were tested using z-test statistics at 0.05 level of significance. The null hypothesis was rejected and the alternate hypotheses accepted when the computed value was greater than the critical value at the significance level of 0.05. On the contrary, the null hypothesis was also accepted and the alternate hypotheses rejected when the computed value is less than the critical table value.

RESULT PRESENTATION

RQ1: *To what extent does which physical resource management influence students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis?*

Table 1: Mean Ratings of Respondents on the Extent physical resource management influence students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis

S/N	Items	Students N= 394		Teachers N=334		Average mean	Std	RMK
		\bar{X}_1	Std ₁	\bar{X}_2	Std ₂			
1.	It helps students optimize their time by organizing materials efficiently, leading to more productive learning study sessions.	3.65	0.89	3.69	0.87	3.67	0.88	HE
2.	Physical resource management improves students focus on their task and reduce distraction.	4.19	1.33	4.20	1.29	4.19	1.31	HE
3.	It enhances academic performance of students.	3.00	0.68	3.02	0.67	3.01	0.68	HE
4.	It helps for stress reduction. A well-managed physical study environment can contribute to reduced stress.	3.07	0.78	3.09	0.78	3.08	0.79	HE
5.	It helps student's develop important skills related to accountability and responsibility by helping them take ownership of their physical resources.	3.00	0.75	3.03	0.74	3.02	0.75	HE
Aggregate Mean/SD for Students and Teachers		3.38	0.89	3.41	0.87	3.39	0.88	HE

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

Table 1, in response to research question 1 which states to what extent does physical resource management influence students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis, had the following opinion scores for both students and teachers. Mean scores of the students to questionnaire items 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 were 3.65, 4.19, 3.00, 3.07 and 3.00 with standard deviations of 0.89, 1.33, 0.68, 0.78 and 0.75 while the mean scores of the teachers were 3.69, 4.20, 3.02, 3.09 and 3.03 with standard deviation of 0.87, 1.29, 0.67, 0.78 and 0.74. Furthermore, the mean set representing the average mean scores for both students and teachers were 3.67, 4.19, 3.01, 3.08 and 3.02; with standard deviation of 0.88, 1.31, 0.68, 0.79 and 0.75 respectively. The readings which were higher than the criterion mean of 3.00 indicated that physical resource management influence students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

RQ. 2: *To what extent does human resource management influence students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis?*

Table 2: Mean Ratings of Respondents on the Extent human resource management influence students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis

S/N	Items	Students N= 394		Teachers N=334		Average mean	Std	RMK
		\bar{X}_1	Std ₁	\bar{X}_2	Std ₂			
6.	It helps students' personal development, by improving their interpersonal skills, communication skills and teamwork capabilities.	4.30	1.24	4.36	1.18	4.33	1.21	VHE
7.	It helps students in career preparation. HR management practices such as resume building, interview preparations etc prepare students for future jobs.	4.54	1.02	4.56	1.01	4.55	1.01	VHE
8.	It helps students in conflict resolution in academic profession and personal setting.	3.48	0.84	3.48	0.81	3.48	0.83	HE
9.	It helps students expand their professional network, leading to improved academic performance and career opportunity.	3.52	0.90	3.51	0.87	3.52	0.89	HE
10.	It improves students' leadership skills and qualities capable of improving their academic performance.	4.69	0.77	4.71	0.73	4.70	0.75	VHE
Aggregate Mean/SD for Students and Teachers		3.91	0.96	4.12	0.92	4.12	0.94	VHE

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

Table 2, in response to research question 2 which states to what extent human resource management influence students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis, had the following opinion scores for both students and teachers. Mean scores of the students to questionnaire items 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10 were 4.30, 4.54, 3.48, 3.52 and 4.69 with standard deviations of 1.24, 1.02, 0.84, 0.90 and 0.77 while the mean scores of the teachers were 4.36, 4.56, 3.48, 3.51 and 4.71 with standard deviation of 1.18, 1.01, 0.81, 0.87 and 0.73. Furthermore, the mean set representing the average mean scores for both students and teacher were 4.33, 4.55, 3.48, 3.52 and 4.70; with standard deviation of 1.21, 1.01, 0.83, 0.89 and 0.75 respectively. The readings which were higher than the criterion mean of 3.00 indicated that human resource management influence students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

RQ. 3: To what extent does financial resource management influence students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis?

Table 3: Mean Ratings of Respondents on the Extent financial resource management influence students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis

S/N	Items	Students N= 394		Teachers N= 334		Average mean	Std	RMK
		\bar{X}_1	Std ₁	\bar{X}_2	Std ₂			
11.	Financial resource management enhanced learning Environment, such as classrooms, laboratories and libraries for students.	3.63	0.78	3.67	0.74	3.65	0.76	HE
12.	It helps for optimal utilization of resources. This helps in avoiding disruptions in learning activities.	3.36	0.74	3.31	0.70	3.34	0.72	HE
13.	It improves safety and comfort. This includes proper lighting, ventilation, seating and clean facilities that enhance students' academic performance.	3.04	0.56	3.03	0.55	3.04	0.56	HE
14.	It increases students' opportunities for practical learning experience that is capable of improving their academic performance.	4.07	0.55	4.06	0.52	4.06	0.53	HE
15.	It ensures equity distribution of resources among all students, reducing disparities, which helps to improve students' academic performance.	4.03	0.63	4.03	0.59	4.17	0.61	HE
Aggregate Mean/SD for Students and Teachers		3.63	0.66	3.60	0.62	3.60	0.64	HE

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

Table 3, in response to research question 3 which states to what extent does financial resource management influence students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis, had the following opinion scores for both male and female students. Mean scores of the students to questionnaire items 11, 12, 13, 14 and 15 were 3.63, 3.36, 3.04, 4.07 and 4.03 with standard deviations of 0.78, 0.74, 0.56, 0.55 and 0.63 while the mean scores of the teachers were 3.67, 3.31, 3.03, 4.06 and 4.03 with standard deviation of 0.74, 0.70, 0.55, 0.52 and 0.59. Furthermore, the mean set representing the average mean scores for both students and teachers were 3.65, 3.34, 3.04, 4.06 and 4.17; with standard deviation of 0.76, 0.72, 0.56, 0.53 and 0.61 respectively. The readings which were higher than the criterion mean of 3.00 indicated that financial resource management influence students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Hypotheses Testing

Ho₁: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of teachers and students on the extent to which physical resource management influence students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Table 4: Z-test Analysis on the Extent physical resource management influence students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Respondents	N	\bar{x}	Std	DF	z-cal	z-crit	LS	Decision
Students	394	3.38	0.89					Accepted
Teachers	334	3.41	0.87	726	0.73	±1.96	0.05	

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

The result on Table 4, above shows Z-test Analysis on the extent physical resource management influence students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis. The result on the table showed that there is no significant difference between the mean responses of teachers and students on how physical resource management influence students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis. The result on the table further showed a z-calculated value of 0.73 which was less than the z-critical value of ± 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance and with a degree of freedom of 726, since the z-calculated (0.73) was less than the z-tabulated (± 1.96), the null hypothesis was accepted which states that there is no significant difference between the mean responses of teachers and students on how physical resource management influence students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of teachers and students on the extent to which human resource management influence students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Table 5: Z-test Analysis on the Extent human resource management influence students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Respondents	N	\bar{x}	Std	DF	z-cal	z-crit	LS	Decision
Students	394	3.91	0.96					Accepted
Teachers	334	4.12	0.92	726	0.51	± 1.96	0.05	

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

The result on Table 5, above shows Z-test Analysis on the extent human resource management influence students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis. The result on the table showed that there is no significant difference between the mean responses of teacher counsellor and students on how human resource management influence students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis. The result on the table further showed a z-calculated value of 0.51 which was less than the z-critical value of ± 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance and with a degree of freedom of 726, since the z-calculated (0.51) was less than the z-tabulated (± 1.96), the null hypothesis was accepted which states there is no significant difference between the mean responses of teachers and students on how human resource management influence students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Ho₃: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of teachers and students' teachers on the extent to which financial resource management influence students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Table 6: Z-test Analysis on the Extent financial resource management influence students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Respondents	N	\bar{x}	Std	DF	z-cal	z-crit	LS	Decision
Students	394	3.63	0.66					Accepted
Teachers	334	3.60	0.62	726	0.27	± 1.96	0.05	

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

The result on Table 6, above shows Z-test Analysis on the extent financial resource management influence students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis. The result on the table showed that there is no significant difference between the mean responses of teacher counsellor and students on how financial resource management influence students' academic performance

in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis. The result on the table further showed a z-calculated value of 0.27 which was less than the z-critical value of ± 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance and with a degree of freedom of 726, since the z-calculated (0.27) was less than the z-tabulated (± 1.96), the null hypothesis was accepted which states that there is no significant difference between the mean responses of teachers and students on how financial resource management influence students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Table 1, in response to research question 1, the readings which were higher than the criterion mean of 3.00 indicated that physical resource management influence students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis. The result on table 4, further showed a z-calculated value of 0.73 which was less than the z-critical value of ± 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance and with a degree of freedom of 726, since the z-calculated (0.73) was less than the z-tabulated (± 1.96), the null hypothesis was accepted which states that there is no significant difference between the mean responses of teachers and students on how physical resource management influence students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis. The findings were in consonant with the previous findings of Lorton and Walley (2016), and Hallack (2014), who discovered that learning experiences are fruitful when there are adequate quality and quantity of physical resources, and that unattractive school buildings, crowded classrooms, non-availability of playing ground and surroundings that have no aesthetic beauty can contribute to poor academic performance.

Table 2, in response to research question 2, the readings which were higher than the criterion mean of 3.00 indicated that human resource management influence students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis. The result on table 5, further showed a z-calculated value of 0.51 which was less than the z-critical value of ± 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance and with a degree of freedom of 726, since the z-calculated (0.51) was less than the z-tabulated (± 1.96), the null hypothesis was accepted which states there is no significant difference between the mean responses of teachers and students on how human resource management influence students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis. The finding was in agreement with Oni (2019), who discovered that human resources played the most important role in the teaching-learning situation than any other factors of production in the school system. Alani (2019) opined that teacher who regularly monitor and supervise their students' learning by checking students' work and helping individual students to overcome errors and learning difficulties are likely to have students who exhibit higher level of achievement. The finding was also in line with Ocho (2015), who submits that the quality of school management of human and material resources has a very strong relationship to the students' academic performance.

Table 3, in response to research question 3, the readings which were higher than the criterion mean of 3.00 indicated that financial resource management influence students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis. The result on table 6, further showed a z-calculated value of 0.27 which was less than the z-critical value of ± 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance and with a degree of freedom of 726, since the z-calculated (0.27) was less than the z-tabulated (± 1.96), the null hypothesis was accepted which states that there is no significant difference between the mean responses of teachers and students on how financial resource management influence students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis. This result is in line with earlier findings of Adeogun (2017), who reported that good education costs more than bad. Inadequacy of funds handicaps principals in their administrative and academic functions. He asserted that education as a social service requires adequate funding to procure, maintain and keep the school services going.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that to a high extent physical resource management, human resource management and financial resource management influence students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis. Physical resources: These include buildings, classrooms,

laboratories, libraries, administrative staff offices, technical equipment and other physical plant like machines, vehicles, computer sets, typewriters, duplicating and photocopy machines. Human resources: These refer to students, teachers, administrative staff, supervising staff from the ministry of education, guidance counselors, school managers etc. Financial resources: These are the monetary inputs available for and expended on the educational system. These are usually referred to as cost of and expenditure on education.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study and conclusion made, the following recommendations were put forward by the researcher:

1. Government should make sure that the resources allocated to the education sectors are properly and judiciously utilized so as to bring about good result.
2. The government, parents and private organizations should rally round to provide educational resources for effective teaching and learning.
3. In order to improve the management of educational resources, trusted and efficient men and women should be employed for the purpose of proper implementation of stated objectives of educational system.
4. Qualified, experienced and endowed persons should be controlling and managing the affairs of the educational institutions so as to utilize the scarce educational resources efficiently and effectively.

REFERENCES

- Adeogun, A.A. (2019). The Principal and Financial Management of Public Secondary Schools in Osun State. *Journal of Educational System and Development*. 5(1), PP. 1-10
- Adeogun, A.A. (2018). Educational Planning and Administration in Africa. *Journal of Studies in Education* 9(1), 147-158.
- Adeogun, A.A. (2017). Economic of Education. Lagos: Olatunji Press and Publishers.
- Aghenta, J.A. (2009). Principles and Practice of Educational Planning: *focus on the Developing Countries*. Benin City: NSCP.
- Ajayi, I.A. (2006). Achieving Universal Basic Education (UBE) in Nigeria: Strategies for Improved Funding and Cost Effectiveness. *Being a lead paper presented at the African Conference on Primary/Basic Education held at University of Botswana, Gaborone. 16th-19th October*.
- Alani, R.O. (2019). Contemporary Issues in Nigeria Education. Lagos: *Triumph Books*.
- Ayo, T.N. (2020). Principal of School Management. London: Macmillan.
- Babalola, J.B. (2016). Overview of Educational Management. In J.B. Babalola, A.O.
- Ayeni, S.O. Adedeji, A.A. Sulyman and M.O. Arikewuyo (Eds). Educational Management: *Theory and practice*. Ibadan: *Codat publications*.
- Banjoko, S.A. (2020). Human Resource Management: An expository Approach. Ibadan: Oluseyi Press Limited.
- Ekundayo, H.T. (2020). Resource Management in Education. In J.B. Babalola, and A.O. Ayeni (Eds). Educational Management: Theories and Tasks. Macmillan Nigeria.
- Hallack, J. (2014). The Analysis of Educational Cost Expenditure. Paris: UNESCO, IIEP.
- Lorton, L. and Walley, P. (2006). Introduction to Early Childhood. New York: *John Willey and Sons Ltd*
- Ocho, L.O. (2005). Issues and Concerns on Education and Life. Enugu: *Institute for Development Studies, University of Nigeria*.
- Ogunsaju, S. (2018). A guide to School Effectiveness in Nigeria: *Laville Publication*.
- Ojo, F. (2007). Human Resource Management: *Theory and Practice*. Lagos: *Pana Publishing*.
- Olagboye, A.A. (2018). Introduction to Educational Management in Nigeria. Lagos: *Daily Graphic Nigeria Limited*.
- Oni, J.O. (2019). Education Resources: An Introduction. Lagos: Abeni Sodipo Press Limited.
- Umoh, S.H. (2017). Continuous Assessment Procedures in Schools. In I.I. Adeyemi (Ed). *Guidance and Counseling in Education*. Ilorin: *Indema Publications*.